

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF NATURAL ZEOLITES FOR PREPARATION FOR TRANSPORTATION AND DRYING OF GASES

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Abstract

The natural zeolites from Aydagh field in Azerbaijan can be applied both without chemical modification and modified, as well as in replacement of syntetic zeolites and aluminum oxides and silica gels in the units preparing gas for transportation at the moment.

Keywords: natural zeolite, heat and acid resistance, gas dehydration, cations, modification.

The high thermal acid resistance of natural zeolite during sorption of a group of cations of alkaline, alkaline earth, rare earth and some heavy metals by clinophyllite, characterized by a molecular sieve structure and containing tuff, allows us to consider this mineral as a very promising sorbent for deep drying of gases. The article presents the results of pilot testing of the natural zeolite of the Aydag deposit of the Republic of Azerbaijan, processed according to the technology of VNIPIGAZ. Processing of natural zeolite was carried out in an environment of aqueous solutions of hydrochloric acid, the concentration of which was 0.25 and 1.0 N. Chemical treatment of natural zeolite was carried out according to the following method: a certain mass of zeolite (fractions 2-5 mm) was loaded into a round-bottomed flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer and water heater. An aqueous solution of one of these chemicals was also poured there. The mass ratios of the solution and natural zeolite ranged from 1:1 to 3:1. Processing of natural zeolite was carried out at temperatures of 70-80 °C with continuous stirring and at different durations. Then the contents of the flask were

placed in a porcelain cup and washed first with tap water and then with distilled water until a neutral reaction. The washed natural zeolite was dried at a temperature of 120-150 °C and calcined in a muffle furnace at a temperature of 350°C for 3 hours. After cooling in the desiccator, the physicochemical properties of the natural zeolite sample were determined. The efficiency of the treatment was evaluated by determining the dynamic adsorption capacity of natural zeolite by water vapor before and after treatment. It was found that the optimal ratio of zeolite solution was a value of 1:1, a change in the ratio did not give a positive result: the optimal processing time of natural zeolite is 2 hours. The results of the conducted studies on the chemical treatment of natural zeolite are shown in Table 1. As can be seen from Table 1, when processing 1.0 n. with HCl solution, the adsorption capacity of natural zeolite in moisture increases by about 25% [1]. When natural zeolite is treated with 0.25 n. HCl solution, its moisture adsorption capacity increases by more than 37%. According to the above method, about 200 kg of natural zeolite was produced using 1.0 n. HCl solution at a pilot plant built at the Azerbaijani GPP.

Table.1

The results of the conducted research on the chemical treatment of natural zeolite

Natural zeolite	Natural zeolite Dynamic adsorption capacity by water vapor, g/100g	Drying capacity by dew point temperature, 0C
Source	4.0	-68
Treated with 1.0 N hydrochloric acid	5.01	-70
Treated with 0.25 n. hydrochloric acid	5.3	-72

Table. 2

Physico-chemical properties of the experimental-industrial natural zeolite

Indicators	Parameters
Appearance	Granules of irregular shape, gray-white color
Granule size, mm	2-5
Bulk density, g/cm ³	0.88
Mechanical crushing strength, kg/mm ²	0.79

The physico-chemical properties of the developed pilot batch of natural zeolite are shown in Table.2. The mechanical strength of a sample of natural zeolite from a pilot batch is approximately 3 times higher than the strength of synthetic NaA zeolite of imported production [1]. Since the activity of zeolites in various chemical processes is mainly related to the acidic properties of the surface [2], the study of surface changes after prolonged operation of natural zeolite, when the capacity of the adsorbent is significantly reduced, was of particular interest. The study of the acidity of the surface was carried out by titration with n-butyl amine in the presence of Gammet and Heller indicators. In the treated samples with clinoptilolite, in contrast to the initial sample, there is a decrease in total acidity by 25-30%, which is explained by the presence of mineral salts caused by acid in its composition. In order to clarify possible structural and surface changes of natural zeolite, a spectral analysis of the initial and treated zeolite with reservoir water was carried out after 45 cycles, IR spectra were taken on a spectrometer of the UR-20 type. The study of the vibrations of the crystal framework of zeolites was carried out in the presence of KBr and NaCl. Zeolite samples were prepared as a suspension in vaseline oil. To study the electroacceptor properties of the surface of natural zeolite, the spectra of adsorbed acetonitrile molecules were studied. In the

coordination compounds of acetonitrile with acid molecules, the absorption band of the valence vibrations of the Ca Na bond shifts to the high-frequency region. During adsorption, absorption bands at 2350 and 2380 cm⁻¹ are observed on the initial clinoptilolite. The appearance of new bands may be due to interaction with components that have migrated to the surface after prolonged operation. The results of long-term operation of natural zeolite at the adsorption pilot plant of the Azerbaijani Gas Processing Plant and the dynamic activity of natural zeolites at various moisture contents during gas drying are shown in Table.3. As can be seen from Table 3, the working activity of natural zeolites in moisture is about 15-20% lower than the activity of NaA grade zeolite. After regeneration of synthetic zeolite at a temperature of 350 °C, its moisture activity was 10.7% by weight, and the dew point of the drained gas was minus 36-38°C [3]. Studies have shown that natural zeolites and adsorbents obtained on their basis make it possible to drain gas to a dew point temperature of minus 40-45°C in the conditions of the North. This is sufficient to prepare gas for transport directly in the fields under climatic environmental conditions. Table 4 presents the main technical and economic characteristics of natural zeolite and NaA.

Table.3

Dynamic activity of natural zeolites at various moisture contents during gas drying

Adsorbent	Raw gas		Moisture content		Dew point, °C	Average dynamic moisture activity g/100g
	Moisture content retention, g/nm ³	Dew point, °C	ppm	g/nm ³		
Synthetic Zeolite NaA	1,5	-12	73,0	0,068	-53	11,2
Natural zeolite of the Ai dag deposit	1,52	-13	156	0,132	-35	8,5

Table.4

Technical and economic characteristics of natural zeolite and NaA.

Indicators	Synthetic Zeolite NaA	Natural zeolite of the Ai dag dep
Adsorption capacity, % by weight: on the flag for hydrocarbons	14-16 2,6-2,9	8-9 1,7-2,0
Drying depth, 0C: 0,1 MPa 3,5 MPa 5,5 MPa	Minus 50-60 Minus 25-32 Minus 20-30	Minus 46-52 Minus 20-26 Minus 15-20
Mechanical crushing strength, kg/mm ²	0,06	0,07
Service life, years	2	More 35
Conditions cost, USD/g	2500-4000	120-230

As can be seen from the table, natural zeolite is not inferior to the degree of drying of natural gas to synthetic, and it is 18-21 times cheaper in terms of cost [4]. Thus, natural zeolite from the Aydag deposit, both in and in modified forms, can be used at existing gas treatment plants for transport instead of synthetic zeolite.

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